

A Study of Vanadyl(IV) Complex of Fluorescein-Part-V

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Previous communications of the author to this journal¹⁻⁴ dealt with the studies of Cu(II), Fe(II), Fe(III), rare-earths and Mn(II) complexes of fluorescein (FLCN). The complexes, without exception, were found insoluble in normal solvents. The magnetic moments, spectral behaviour, solid state conductivities, thermal degradation and mössbauer spectrum in the case of Fe(III) complex indicate that these complexes are polymeric and there is a considerable metal-metal interaction as seen from their magnetic behaviour. The present paper gives an account of UV, visible and IR spectra and magnetic behaviour of Vanadyl(IV) complex of fluorescein and thus forms a part of the series of an account of fluorescein complexes studied by the author. V-O frequency changes, taking place in the complex, are described in detail. The structure of the complex is tentatively assigned as

A possibility of NH₃, amines entering the available position on vanadium ion is suggested.

THE oxovanadium(IV) ion with an electronic configuration Ar (3d)¹ is the most stable biatomic ion known and possesses some unusual properties. It has a very strong and dominant axial field and the bonding scheme given by Ballhausen and Gray⁵ suggests a very strong σ bond between (2p_z+2s) hybrid of oxygen and (3dZ²+4s) hybrid of the vanadium ion. The present worker has published his work on the fluorescein complexes of Cu(II), Fe(II), Fe(III) and rare-earths and stumbled upon some unusual properties of these complexes. The investigation of vanadyl(IV) complex of fluorescein was undertaken partly to find whether the properties of vanadyl(IV) complex fall in line with others.

Experimental

Preparation of the metal complex:

100 ml of dilute alcoholic solution (~0.03M) of fluorescein was added slowly to 150 ml of 0.02M solution of vanadyl chloride. The pH was around 7.2. After about six hours of continuous stirring, reddish brown precipitate appeared and changed to dark brown after eighteen hours and remained the same thereafter. The precipitate was washed several times with water-ethanol mixture till it was free of excess of fluorescein and vanadium and chloride ions. It was dried at 120° in partial vacuum.

Analysis:

	C	H	V
Found	69.18	3.41	3.81
Calculated for O=V(FLCN) ₄	69.76	3.19	3.70

The complex was found to be insoluble in all normal solvents. Magnetic, spectral and other measurements were done as reported earlier¹⁻⁴.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic behaviour of the vanadyl complex of fluorescein, as seen from Table 1, is rather unusual. The complex follows the Curie-Weiss behaviour in the temperature range 82.5°K to 288.5°K beyond

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF VANADYL FLUORESCEIN COMPLEX

T°(K)	Corr. $\chi_M \times 10^6$ c.g.s.	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
82.5	3318	1.48
111.2	2557	1.52
146.8	2007	1.54
181.2	1659	1.56
216.0	1411	1.57
254.0	1276	1.62
288.5	1170	1.65
302.5	1229	1.73
324.5	1262	1.81
330.0	1309	1.87
344.0	1386	1.96
350.4	1109	1.82
378.6	1459	2.11
389.5	1449	2.13
404.5	1489	2.19

which it shows considerable deviation. It varies from 1.48 B.M. at 82.5°K to 2.19 B.M. at 404.5°K.

It is expected that NH_3 , amines should form an adduct with the vanadyl complex of fluorescein occupying the vacant position trans to $\text{V}=\text{O}$. Investigation in this direction is in progress in this laboratory.

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